

IMPROVING THE WRITING SKILLS OF STUDENTS.

Abdiolimova Qizlarxon Subhonali qizi
Qahhorova Mavluda Mukarramovna

Farg'ona davlat universiteti
nemis va fransuz tillari kafedrası mudiri
filologiya fanlari nomzodi, professor
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Annotation: Advanced writing skills are an important aspect of academic performance as well as of subsequent work related performance. However, American students rarely attain advanced scores on assessments of writing skills (National Assessment of Educational Progress, 2002). In order to achieve higher levels of writing performance, the working memory demands of writing processes should be reduced so that executive attention is free to coordinate interactions among them.

Key words: writing skill, effective writing, thinking, ability cohesive text, interaction, generating, planning.

Effective writing skills are central both in higher education and the world of work that follows. One's ability to compose an extended text is the single best predictor of success in course work during the freshman year (Geiser & Studley, 2001). Gains in informative and analytical writing ability are, moreover, taken as a good indicator of the value added by higher education (Benjamin & Chun, 2003). Finally, a large share of the value added by businesses in a knowledge-based economy is codified in written documents, placing a premium on a literate workforce (Brandt, 2005).

Despite the importance of writing skills, the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP, 2002) has painted a dismal picture of the writing preparedness of American students. Less than a third of students in 4th grade (28%), 8th grade (31%), and 12th grade (21%) scored at or above proficient levels. Only 2% wrote at an advanced level for all three samples. Although writing scores had reliably improved for 4th and 8th graders since the 1998 testing, they decreased slightly for 12th graders.

Writing well is a major cognitive challenge, because it is at once a test of memory, language, and thinking ability. It demands rapid retrieval of domain-specific knowledge about the topic from long-term memory (Kellogg, 2001). A high degree of verbal ability is necessary to generate cohesive text that clearly expresses the ideational content (McCutchen, 1984). Writing ability further

depends on the ability to think clearly about substantive matters (Nickerson, Perkins, & Smith, 1985).

Finally, working memory is severely taxed by the production of extended texts. Representations of the author's intended ideas, the meaning of the text as it is written, and even the possible meanings of the text as construed by the imagined readers need to be transiently maintained during text production (Traxler & Gernsbacher, 1992). Moreover, mature writers concurrently juggle the planning of ideas, the generation of text, and the reviewing of ideas and text, placing heavy demands on executive attention (Hayes & Flower, 1980; Kellogg, 1996). Given these demands, it is not surprising that both developmental and individual differences in writing ability can be explained in terms of the limitations of working memory (McCutchen, 1996). One must have the capacity to maintain multiple representations and to control the interactions among planning, generation, and reviewing in order to write well.

Cognitive science has focused more on numeracy and the reading side of literacy than on writing (Levy, 1997). Even so, several findings have implications for the design of writing instruction, as noted in previous reviews of the literature (Hayes & Flower, 1986; Rijlaarsdam et al., 2005). Our focus here is on a principle found useful in training complex skills but relatively overlooked to date in the field of written composition. Deliberate practice has been proven highly effective in training performance on related tasks, such as typing (one motor output for writing), chess (another planning-intensive task), and music (another creative production task). The very best violinists, for example, have accumulated more than 10,000 h in solitary practice, whereas lesser experts (7,500 h), least accomplished experts (5,000 h), and amateurs (1,500 h) have devoted proportionately less time to self improvement (K. A. Ericsson, Krampe, & Tesch-Römer, 1993). We suggest that deliberate practice theoretically offers a too infrequently exploited means to attain the working memory control required in writing.

In what follows, we first briefly review some facts on the importance of cognitive control in writing skill. We then present the elements of deliberate practice in the training of college-level writers and evidence of their importance. Finally, we discuss difficulties in implementing deliberate practice in writing instruction.

Cognitive Control in Writing

Composing an extended text appears to require the selfregulation of planning, text generation, and reviewing through metacognitive control of these processes (Graham & Harris, 2000; Zimmerman & Risemberg, 1997). All three basic processes require executive attention, in addition to maintaining representations in the verbal, visual, and spatial stores of working memory (Kellogg, Olive, & Piolat, 2007). Mature writing requires numerous transitions among planning, generation, and reviewing (Hayes & Flower, 1980; Levy & Ransdell, 1995), as the author attempts to solve the content problem of what to say and the rhetorical problem of how to say it (Bereiter & Scardamalia, 1987; Scardamalia & Bereiter, 1991). Three facts indicate that self-regulatory control of written production depends on having adequate working memory resources.

First, measures of working memory capacity correlate with writing performance (Ransdell & Levy, 1996). This is but one instance of a wide range of complex cognitive tasks, including tests of fluid intelligence, that are uniquely predicted by one's ability to control processing through executive attention (Engle, Tuholski, Laughlin, & Conway, 1999). Neuroimaging of the frontal lobe regions linked to executive attention in working memory also reveal greater activation in individuals with high fluid g than in those with low fluid g (Duncan et al., 2000). Converging experimental results show that distracting executive attention with a concurrent task disrupts both the quality and fluency of text composition (Ransdell, Levy, & Kellogg, 2002).

Second, children's fluency in generating written text is limited until they master the mechanical skills of handwriting and spelling (McCutchen, 1996). Learning the mechanics of writing to a point of automaticity during primary school years frees the components of working memory for planning, generating, and reviewing (Graham, Berninger, Abbott, Abbott, & Whitaker, 1997). Mastery of handwriting and spelling is also a necessary condition for writers to begin to develop the control of cognition, emotion, and behavior that is needed to sustain the production of texts (Graham & Harris, 2000).

Third, advancement to the use of writing as a means of thinking, as well as language production, emerges only after a decade or so of writing experience. In late adolescence and young adulthood, writers move beyond merely telling the reader what the author knows (Bereiter & Scardamalia, 1987). Mature adult authors transform their own ideas as a consequence of generating text and reviewing their ideas and text. They come to use writing as a way of thinking through matters and constructing new knowledge structures in long-term

memory. Reviewing the text often triggers more planning that transforms the author's ideas about the topic. Reviewing can also trigger more language generation to reduce the difference between what the author means and what the text says at the moment.

Such knowledge transforming requires concurrent representations in working memory of the author's ideas and the text's meaning (Traxler & Gernsbacher, 1992). It also requires the coordination of complex interactions among planning, generating, and reviewing. As McCutchen (1996) documented in her review of the literature, each of these basic processes is constrained by working memory limitations. The number and qualitative nature of processes that a writer can coordinate at once depend on attaining sufficient fluency with each process. Absent mastery of and cognitive control over planning, generation, and reviewing, writers appear to never move beyond knowledge telling.

Several factors no doubt underlie the development of cognitive control in writing. These include (1) the maturation of working memory throughout adolescence (Sowell, Thompson, Holmes, Jernigan, & Toga, 1999), (2) learning strategies for prewriting, drafting, and revision that manage the demands of composition (Fayol, 1999), and (3) rapid retrieval of domain-specific knowledge from long-term memory when needed during composition, thus avoiding the need for transient storage in short-term working memory (Kellogg, 2001; McCutchen, 2000). However, the use of deliberate practice to reduce directly the working memory demands of each writing process offers an obvious and potentially valuable alternative that has yet to be fully realized in writing education.

Conclusion

Deliberate practice, we suggest, should be a fundamental principle that guides the instruction and training of student writers. As with the acquisition of other complex physical and cognitive skills, acquiring expertise in the writing of extended texts takes many years of deliberate practice. Presumably, such practice helps writers to gain cognitive control over text production by reducing the individual working memory demands of planning ideas, text generation, and reviewing ideas and text. A writer's ability to use linguistic and domain-specific knowledge in composing a text and in solving the content and rhetorical problems it poses depends on achieving such control.

That only 2% of high school seniors achieve an advanced score on the NAEP test of writing skill may be at least in part a consequence of insufficient or poorly

designed practice. Research is needed, in our view, on the best ways to implement deliberate practice in educational interventions, including application of the spacing effect and advances in automated essay scoring. Such applied cognitive research has the potential for making significant improvements in writing education.

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